

Studies in the Condensation of Di-*ortho*-thiobenzoic Acid with Aromatic Hydroxy Compounds.

BY RAJENDRA NATH SEN AND SURESH CHANDRA SEN-GUPTA.

The interaction between di-*ortho*-thiobenzoic acid and simple aromatic compounds such as benzene, xylene, *p*-chloro-phenol, in presence of concentrated sulphuric acid was studied by Prescott and Smiles (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1911, **99**, 640) and by Marsden and Smiles (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1911, **99**, 1353), who observed that the di-*ortho*-thiobenzoic acid, in presence of sulphuric acid and a simple aromatic compound, splits up into a mercaptan and a sulphylic acid; the latter substance then condenses with aromatic compounds to form thioxanthenes, and "the remaining mercaptan is reoxidised by the sulphuric acid to the original disulphide. Thus sulphur dioxide is continually liberated during the reaction, and the rupture of the disulphide continues."

In the present work, the condensations of di-*ortho*-thiobenzoic acid specially with aromatic hydroxy compounds have been investigated with a view to prepare and study thioxanthone dyes. In this connection several interesting observations have been made regarding the reaction and the tinctorial character of the resulting products,

Thus the three cresols condense with the acid in presence of sulphuric acid at 95°–100°. The products obtained are the three methylhydroxy-thioxanthenes.

(I).

1-Methyl-4-hydroxy-thioxanthone.

(II).

3-Methyl-2-hydroxy-thioxanthone.

(III).

4-Methyl-2-hydroxy-thioxanthone.

These three compounds readily dissolve in alkali hydroxide solution, from which they are easily separated by saturating the solution with carbon dioxide, and they all form monobenzoyl derivatives. The introduction of one auxochrome group (OH) into the simple thioxanthone chromogen brings out the tinctorial properties of the compounds which are all yellow, and dye wool light yellow shades. The behaviour of these compounds on reduction is quite interesting. Thus when reduced with zinc dust in caustic soda solution, the reduction products, which are presumably xanthidols, are colourless but on adding hydrochloric acid pink colour appears, which is probably due to salt formation with elimination of water and production of an *o*-quinonoid configuration.

p-Nitro-phenol is found to be far more reactive than the cresols and condenses with the di-thio-acid readily. This is due to the presence of nitro group in the nucleus. The product (IV) dissolves in alkali hydroxide solution from which it is not precipitated with carbon dioxide, which is due to the increased acidic property of the OH group in presence of a nitro group in the nucleus. The

compound possesses a brownish black colour and the ammonium salt dyes wool in blackish brown shade from an acid bath.

The condensation products of the di-thio-acid with the di-hydroxy benzenes have offered a very interesting study.

Catechol condenses with the di-*o*-thio-benzoic acid producing 1:2-dihydroxy-thioxanthone (V). The compound is brown and dissolves in alkali hydroxide solution with crimson colour, from which carbon dioxide precipitates the compound.

It has been given this constitution from analogy with alizarine. Like alizarine it possesses very marked polygenetic properties dyeing wool greenish black with iron mordant and beautiful chocolate shade with chromium mordant. Thus replacing one CO group in alizarin by sulphur, the polygenetic property of the dyestuff is not affected, although it is very remarkable that alumina mordanted cotton is dyed a yellow shade only.

Resorcin also condenses with the acid at 95°–100°. The analyses of the product (VI) and its potassium and silver salts indicate the condensation of two molecules of sulphoxylic acid with one molecule of resorcinol, and also the sulphonation of the resulting product (the position of the sulphonic acid group being uncertain). The green condensation product gives a green solution in water and a red solution with alkalis. If CO₂ be passed into the red alkaline solution no precipitation takes place nor does the original green colour reappear; but on neutralising the solution with HCl, the green colour reappears and on adding excess of HCl the green compound separates out; this behaviour is in perfect agreement with the presence of carboxyl and sulphonic acid groups. Further the analysis of the potassium salt of the compound shows that a tetrapotassium salt is formed as expected. The presence of a carboxyl and a sulphonic acid group is also supported by the following observations.

When the red aqueous ammoniacal solution of the compound is dried on the water-bath, ammonia is given off and the dried mass thus obtained gives a pale reddish yellow solution much lighter than the original solution; and the silver salt obtained from this

ammonium salt shows on analysis that a di-silver salt (VII) has been formed, which is best accounted for by assuming that the ammonium groups replacing the hydrogen atoms of the hydroxyl groups have been eliminated as ammonia when heated,

and that the ammonium groups replacing the H of the carboxyl and sulphonic acid groups only have been replaced by Ag. Again the silver salt obtained by adding silver nitrate solution directly to the aqueous solution of the compound shows, on analysis, that the same di-silver salt is formed, confirming the presence of two acid groups in the molecule. It may be noted that no lactone formation takes place in this compound though such a possibility exists. The colour of the compound is deep green and it dyes wool in green shade from an acid bath. This compound is readily soluble in water and alcohol, but another product, obtained by heating resorcin with the di-thioacid in presence of sulphuric acid at 120°-130° for about one hour, is found to be quite insoluble in water and alcohol though it is green like the former compound. This product, however, has not been obtained in a sufficiently pure condition for analysis.

Now the *o*-dihydroxy-thioxanthone (V) is brown and *p*-dihydroxy-thioxanthone (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1911, 99, 1535) is orange but the compound (VI) which is a derivative of *m*-dihydroxy-thioxanthone is green. It can hardly be expected that such a deep colour is due only to the difference in position of the hydroxyl groups; it is probable that the colour is also influenced by the presence of the additional group—S.C₆H₄.CO₂H. In order to decide whether such a deep colour is consistent with the simple constitution attributed to the compound, resorcin dimethyl ether has been condensed with the acid, in which case possibility of lactone formation is excluded.

The condensation product (VIII) is also found to be bluish green. It is insoluble in water but soluble in alkali carbonate solution with a red colour and therefore contains a free carboxyl group. It is found, however, not to have been sulphonated and it gives a mono-potassium salt only. By replacing the two hydroxyl groups of the

compound (VI) by two methoxyl groups, the colour of the compound only changes from deep green to bluish green.

In order to study the effect of an additional hydroxyl group, pyrogallol is condensed with the di-thio-acid. The condensation takes place with two molecules of the sulphylic acid. The product (IX) is readily soluble in alkali carbonate solution indicating a free carboxyl group.

When acetylated it gives a tri-acetyl derivative. The compound shows very marked polygenetic properties dyeing wool green with chromium mordant and greenish black with iron mordant. Aluminium mordanted cotton is dyed a brown shade. The condensation product of phloroglucinol with the di-thio-acid may be (Xa) or the

reaction may proceed a step further producing a lactone (Xb) (xanthone formation being not possible). The analysis supports the formula (Xb). The compound dissolves in alkali hydroxide solution from which it is reprecipitated with HCl but not by CO₂, this being undoubtedly due to the scission of the lactone ring and formation of an alkali salt of the carboxyl group. The ammonium salt of the compound dyes wool a light brownish shade from an acid bath. The product (XI) obtained by condensing β-naphthol with the acid is a disulphonic acid. In this compound the sulphur is attached to the

α -position and consequently, in this case also, lactone-ring formation takes place.

It gives a tetra-potassium salt, the lactone ring being broken up. The compound is greenish-black and dyes wool in a light brownish-yellow shade from an acid bath.

In order to prepare other mordant thio-xanthone dyes in this group, salicylic acid, 1:2:3- and 1:2:5-cresotinic acids have been condensed with the di-thio-acid. The condensation product (XII) with salicylic acid is obtained as a mono-sulphonic acid compound, which is brownish yellow, the position of the sulphonic acid group being uncertain.

Though it contains OH and COOH groups in α -position to each other, it does not, however, show polygenetic properties. It dyes both iron and chromium mordanted wool yellow shades with slight difference. The condensation products with cresotinic acids, however, show polygenetic properties by qualitative tests.

EXPERIMENTAL.

The di- α -thiobenzoic acid used in the condensations was prepared from anthranillic acid. Anthranillic acid (28 g.) was mixed with hydrochloric acid (d 1.19, 48 c.c. and 100 c.c. water) and then diazotised by the addition of a conc. aqueous solution of sodium nitrite, (about 14 g.) keeping the temperature below 3°. The diazo-solution was then slowly run in with constant stirring into a solution containing sulphur (6.7 g.) and sodium sulphide (52 g.) in 58 c.c. of water to which 24 gm. of aqueous caustic soda (d 1.38) had been previously added. Throughout the operation the temperature was kept below +5° by the addition of ice. After a short

* The condensation product of β -naphthol-6:3-disulphonic acid with the di-thio-acid, obtained under similar conditions, exhibits properties similar to those of compound (XI) indicating the positions of the SO₃H groups. As however it was prepared only in a small quantity and not in a sufficiently pure condition, the percentage of sulphur was a little too low.

time the temperature gradually rose up due to the formation of di-*ortho*-thiobenzoic acid. After two hours, the clear solution of the sodium salt of the acid was filtered from the unacted upon sulphur which separated out. Hydrochloric acid was then added to the solution until it was acid to congo red paper, and the precipitated di-thio-acid was filtered and thoroughly washed.

1-Methyl-4-hydroxythioxanthone (I).—The di-thio-acid (5 g., 1 mol.) and *p*-cresol (5 g., 2 mols.) were mixed with sulphuric acid (10 c.c., *d* 1.84). The reaction started at the ordinary temperature but was completed by heating the mixture on boiling water-bath for about 8 hours. Pounded ice was then added to the mixture and the yellow mass was thoroughly washed with cold water to remove sulphuric acid. It was then dissolved in hot caustic soda solution, filtered and the solution was saturated with carbon dioxide, when the methyl-hydroxy-thioxanthone separated out. It was then filtered, thoroughly washed with water and, after drying, crystallised from hot (50°-60°) absolute alcohol as yellow, shining, silky, microcrystals, m.p. 234° with decomposition. It is soluble in hot alcohol, glacial acetic acid, pyridine, and slightly soluble in chloroform. The *sodium salt* of the compound crystallises from water in orange yellow needles. The *ammonium salt* dyes wool a greenish yellow shade from an acid bath. (Found: S, 13.2; C, 69.3; H, 4.2. $C_{14}H_{10}O_2S$ requires S, 13.2; C, 69.4; H, 4.1 per cent.)

Benzoyl derivative.—The benzoyl derivative was prepared in the cold. It was crystallised from a mixture of alcohol and chloroform as yellow microcrystalline powder melting at 176°-177°. It readily dissolves in chloroform but is insoluble in alcohol. (Found: S, 9.0. $C_{21}H_{14}O_3S$ requires S, 9.2 per cent.)

3-Methyl-2-hydroxythioxanthone (II).—The condensation was carried out as in the case of *p*-cresol, and the product purified similarly. It was obtained as a yellow microcrystalline powder melting at 210°-212°. It is soluble in absolute alcohol, glacial acetic acid and pyridine. Its *ammonium salt* dyes wool greenish yellow shade from an acid bath. (Found: S, 13.25; C, 69.19; H, 4.2. $C_{14}H_{10}O_2S$ requires S, 13.2; C, 69.19; H, 4.1 per cent.)

The *benzoyl derivative* was prepared and purified as in the case the benzoyl derivative of 1-methyl-4-hydroxy-thioxanthone. It was obtained as pale yellow crystalline powder melting at 129°-130°. (Found: S, 9.3. $C_{21}H_{14}O_3S$ requires S, 9.2 per cent.)

4-Methyl-2-hydroxythioxanthone (III).—The condensation was carried on as in the case of *p*-cresol. The reaction being completed, ice water was added to the mixture and the soft pasty mass hardened on keeping overnight. It was then purified as in the case of 1-methyl-4-hydroxy-thioxanthone. It crystallises from absolute alcohol as yellow microcrystalline powder which begins to shrink on heating above 170° and melts with decomposition at 190°. The ammonium salt dyes wool in a greenish yellow shade from an acid bath. It is soluble in alcohol, glacial acetic acid and pyridine. (Found: S, 13·3 ; C, 69·2 ; H, 4·4. $C_{14}H_{10}O_2S$ requires S, 13·2 ; C, 69·4 ; H, 4·1 per cent.)

1-Nitro-4-hydroxythioxanthone (IV).—Equal amounts of *p*-nitrophenol and the di-thio-acid were mixed with conc. sulphuric acid when much heat was evolved. The mixture was heated on the water-bath at 80° for about 2 hours. The product was thoroughly washed with cold water, dissolved in caustic soda solution, filtered and precipitated with hydrochloric acid. It was then dried and extracted with pyridine. On pouring the pyridine solution in alcohol, the compound separated out in microcrystalline form. It does not melt on heating to 280°. The compound is brownish; the ammonium salt dyes wool a blackish brown shade from an acid bath. (Found: S, 11·9 ; C, 56·8 ; H, 2·7. $C_{13}H_7O_4NS$ requires S, 11·7 ; C, 57·1 ; H, 2·5 per cent.)

1:2-Dihydroxy-thioxanthone (V) was prepared and purified as usual. It was necessary to recrystallise the compound several times from absolute alcohol in order to get it pure. It is a brown crystalline powder melting at 245°-248° with decomposition. It dyes wool a beautiful chocolate shade with chromium mordant and greenish black with iron mordant; alumina mordanted cotton is also dyed a bright yellow shade. It is soluble in alcohol and pyridine. (Found: S, 13·5 ; C, 63·5 ; H, 3·6. $C_{13}H_8O_3S$ requires S, 13·1 ; C, 63·9 ; H, 3·3 per cent.)

Condensation of Di-o-thiobenzoic acid with Resorcin.—Resorcin (3 g.), the di-thio-acid (3 g.) and concentrated sulphuric acid (8 c.c.) were heated on boiling water-bath for 8 hours. The pink mass, on adding water, changed to green. The product being soluble in water, was poured in dilute hydrochloric acid (1:1) and set aside overnight. The precipitate was thoroughly washed with dilute HCl to remove sulphuric acid and was dissolved in the least amount of hot water, filtered and a little strong HCl was added to the solution

when the product gradually separated out. It was then filtered and washed thoroughly with dilute HCl. The product was then dried and extracted with hot alcohol in which it dissolved readily. A few drops of hydrochloric acid were added to the alcoholic solution and in a short time the product separated out. It was then filtered, thoroughly washed with dilute HCl to remove traces of sulphuric acid and was dried in an air-bath at 110°-120°, as it tenaciously retained some water. The compound does not melt when heated even to 280°. It dyes wool green from an acid bath. It is soluble in alcohol and pyridine. (Found: S, 20·2; C, 50·1; H, 2·7. $C_{20}H_{12}O_8S_3$ requires S, 20·1; C, 50·4; H, 2·5 per cent.)

The *potassium salt* of the above compound was prepared by adding 0·5 gm. of the substance to a solution of about 0·3 gm. of pure caustic potash and the filtered solution evaporated to dryness on the water-bath. The dried salt was quickly powdered and thoroughly washed with absolute alcohol to remove any excess of caustic potash. The potassium salt was obtained as red powder. (Found: K, 24·3. $C_{20}H_8O_8S_3K_4$ requires K, 24·8 per cent.)

The potassium salt obtained by adding alcoholic potash to the alcohol solution of the compound gives a low percentage of potassium, which may be due to simultaneous separation of di- and tri-potassium salts.

Silver salt.—The compound was dissolved in aqueous ammonia, and evaporated to dryness on water-bath. The dried ammonium salt was dissolved in water and silver nitrate solution added when the silver salt separated out. (Found: Ag, 31·6. $C_{14}H_{10}O_8S_3Ag_2$ requires Ag, 31·3 per cent.)

Condensation of Di-o-thiobenzoic acid with Resorcin dimethyl-ether (VIII).—The condensation is carried out as described above. Ice-water is then added and the solid product washed with cold water. It is extracted with cold dilute sodium carbonate solution from which dilute HCl precipitates the compound. The process is repeated and the product washed with water. It is dried in an air-bath at 110°-120°. The compound is bluish green but its K-salt is red. It is insoluble in common organic solvents and does not melt on heating even to 280°. It dyes wool a light blue shade from sulphuric acid solution largely diluted with water. (Found: C, 61·7; H, 4·0; OMe, 14·0. $C_{22}H_{16}O_5S_2$ requires C, 62·2; H, 3·7; OMe, 14·6 per cent.)

The *K-salt* was prepared as in the case of the resorcin compound. (Found: K, 9.1. $C_{22}H_{15}O_5S_2K$ requires K, 8.6 per cent.)

*Condensation of Di-o-thiobenzoic acid with Pyrogallol (IX).—*The condensation is carried out as described before. The product is extracted with hot alcohol (absolute) from which it is obtained as a grey powder. It gives a red alkaline solution and is insoluble in water and in other common organic solvents except alcohol. It does not melt on heating even to 280° . It shows polygenetic properties dyeing wool green with chromium mordant and greenish black with iron mordant. It also dyes alumina mordanted cotton a brown shade. (Found: C, 57.9; H, 3.2. $C_{20}H_{12}O_6S_2$ requires C, 58.2; H, 2.9 per cent.)

The *acetyl derivative* is prepared by heating the compound with acetic anhydride and fused zinc chloride to 130° for 15 mins. It was crystallised from chloroform as a light brown powder. (Found: CH_3CO , 24.3. $C_{20}H_9O_6S_2(CH_3CO)_3$ requires CH_3CO , 23.9 per cent.)

*Condensation of Di-o-thiobenzoic acid with Phloroglucinol.—*The product was dissolved in caustic soda solution, precipitated with dilute HCl, filtered, washed, dried and crystallised from absolute alcohol. It was thus obtained as pinkish needles, melting at 166° . It is soluble in alcohol and pyridine. (Found: S, 12.2; C, 60.1; H, 3.0. $C_{13}H_8O_4S$ requires S, 12.2; C, 60.0; H, 3.0 per cent.)

The *ammonium salt* of the compound dyes wool in a light brownish red shade from an acid bath.

*Condensation of Di-o-thiobenzoic acid with β -Naphthol.—*The dithioacid (4 g.) and β -naphthol (4 g.) are mixed up with 15 c.c. of sulphuric acid and heated at 95° - 100° for 15 hours. The mixture is poured in dilute hydrochloric acid (1:1) and allowed to stand overnight. The compound separates out and is filtered and washed with moderately dilute HCl, until free from sulphuric acid, and then dried in the steam-bath, extracted with hot absolute alcohol, from which the compound separates out on the addition of benzene as a greenish black powder. It does not melt when heated even to 280° . It is soluble in alcohol and pyridine.

It dyes wool a light brownish yellow shade from an acid bath. (Found: S, 22.4; C, 46.4; H, 2.3. $C_{17}H_{10}O_8S_3$ requires S, 21.9; C, 46.5; H, 2.4 per cent.)

The *tetra-potassium salt* was prepared by adding 1 gm. of the compound to a dilute solution of pure caustic potash containing about

0.4 gm. of KOH. The solution was evaporated to dryness, and the powdered salt washed thoroughly with absolute alcohol. (Found: K, 25.1. $C_{17}H_9O_9S_3K_4$ requires K, 25.6 per cent.)

*Condensation of Di-o-thiobenzoic acid with Salicylic acid (XII).—*The product was dried and then washed with a little chloroform to remove any free salicylic acid, and obtained as a brownish yellow powder from hot alcoholic solution. It does not melt on heating to 285° . It dyes wool a bright yellow shade with iron and chromium mordant producing only slight difference in shade. It is soluble in alcohol and pyridine. (Found: S, 18.4; C, 47.8; H, 2.4. $C_{14}H_8O_7S_2$ requires S, 18.1; C, 47.7; H, 2.2 per cent.).

Condensation of Di-o-thiobenzoic acid with 1:2:3- and 1:2:5-Cresotinic acids.—The di-thio-acid (1 mol.) and cresotinic acid (2 mols.) were taken.

The product from 1:2:3-cresotinic acid dyes iron mordanted wool brownish red shade and chromium mordanted wool a pinkish shade.

The compound from 1:2:5-cresotinic acid dyes chromium mordanted wool yellowish green shade and iron mordanted wool a brown shade.

N.B.—Sulphur in all the compounds has been estimated by fusion with sodium peroxide as Carius' method was found not to be very suitable.

